

Balancing Ethics, Legislation and Cultural Heritage: Archiving Sensitive Petsamo Interviews

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Introduction to the Petsamo Research interviews

The Petsamo region holds a unique place in Finnish history. Petsamo was part of Finland 1920–1944 and over 5,500 people were internally displaced to other parts of Finland when the region was ceded to Soviet Union in September 1944. My doctoral dissertation in cultural history focused on how Petsamo people and their offspring see the history of the region and its people, what meanings they attached to it and how they pass them on to new generations.

The oral history interviews were conducted 2013–2017, some of them originally as a part of my master's thesis and for my thesis in minor subject. Most of the interviews were conducted as part of my doctoral dissertation.¹ My aim was to create space for the interviewees to speak freely and bring up perspectives that might not appear in the previous presentations of Petsamo history. The interviewees trusted me with their political opinions and ethnic background among other elements of special categories of personal data. From the very beginning, I took a careful approach on how to process their personal data.

I informed all interviewees when the interviews took place that the aim is eventually to archive the interviews. One of the options was the Regional Museum of Lapland that locates in Rovaniemi Arctic Centre and that is responsible for preserving the history of Petsamo. I kept them informed throughout the years and updated my practices in data protection when general data protection regulation and national act took effect. I had reserved the opportunity to continue my research in ten years after completing my dissertation in 2021. In 2025 I felt it was a good time to start the archiving process as I was no longer active in Petsamo history research. I contacted the museum curator Heidi Pelkonen and discussed the principles of data protection and minimization and what data would serve the purpose of the future research. Based on this discussion and other themes introduced in this report, I decided to archive the transcriptions of the interviews.

Archiving Process: Five-Step Implementation

The first step was to call my interviewees in November 2025 to inform them that I was now going to archive the interviews at the Regional Museum of Lapland. This was to hear their thoughts about archiving and if someone would object to it. I would not have archived the interviews without their ethical consent.

¹ Harjumaa 2015a; Harjumaa 2015b; Harjumaa 2021.

Some of the interviewees were already deceased and information no longer reached them. However, they knew that my purpose was to eventually to archive the interviews, so I saw no ethical or legislative obstacle for continuing with the process. The ones who I called were delighted to hear about me and the archiving with the museum. The second step was to give them more detailed information via email or post, including the museum's Privacy Notice that the curator had sent me.

The third step was once again taking care of the principle of data minimization. I went through the transcriptions several times to delete irrelevant information and especially to protect the identity of the anonymous interviewees. One of the anonymous interviewees suggested that the interview could be archived with identifying information. We drew up a separate agreement for this.

The fourth step was to create metadata and index terms for the interviewees. The museum instructed to create index according to Finnish Thesaurus and Ontology Service (finto.fi).

Finally I delivered the transcriptions, README file, index terms and other attachments as .docx, .pdf or .pdf/A files to the museum's curator Heidi Pelkonen on January 2026.² We signed a transfer agreement whose terms and conditions we had decided on together. Ownership of the material was transferred to the museum. The data is for research purposes only and restricted to the museum premises due to its sensitive nature.

Ethical and Legal Considerations in Archiving

“The Dead Are Still Dear to Us”

The laws and practices relating to the processing of personal data were undergoing changes during my research. When I began the interviews, the previous legislation was still in force before the General Data Protection Regulation (2016/679)³ and National Act (1050/2018)⁴ came into effect in 2018. At that time, I updated the research notices and the legal basis for processing personal data.

Finnish libraries, archives and museums have published instruction on how to handle personal data in these LAM organisations (in Finnish *KAM-sektori*). They emphasize the importance of personal data for understanding the culture and history of communities and stress that excessive anonymization can significantly reduce the value of the data. Similarly, The National Archives of Finland notes that anonymization may weaken the reliability, authenticity and future use of the research data. The updated instructions also focus on Faro convention⁵ that Finland acceded in 2018: everyone has a right for cultural heritage that may be for example beliefs, knowledge, traditions and values that are drawn from the past.⁶ Therefore it was important to find a balance between the regulation, legislation and

² Please see the Attachment 1.

³ General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679.

⁴ Tietosuoja laki 1050/2018.

⁵ Council of Europe Framework Convention on the Value of Cultural Heritage for Society 2005.

⁶ Tietosuoja KAM-sektorilla 21.1.2025, 6; Kansallisarkisto 2026.

instructions on archiving sensitive personal data. I used these publications when considering what is available, necessary and suitable for archiving.

One of the key insights came from a conversation I had with one of the interviewees in November 2025. The interviewee told me how sad it was to see new generations of Petsamo people keep digging up even the most detailed and sensitive information about their deceased relatives: "Even though we are talking about people who are already dead, the dead are still dear to us." The conversation confirmed my view on how we still have ethical responsibility of the deceased people we are studying and related to, even if their personal data is available for use under personal data legislation: the GDPR only applies to living persons.

Understanding public interest in Archiving Sensitive Data

In libraries, archives and museums the processing of personal data is in many cases based on a task in public interest. It was a surprise to read the instructions by The Finnish Data Protection Ombudsman:

[T]he purpose of the archiving [*special categories of personal data*] must be in the public interest. Archiving could be necessary for the public interest if the controller has a statutory or regulatory duty to store research data and make it available. Another important consideration is whether the archiving activities are based on a plan available to the public. The Data Protection Act's concept of archiving purposes in the public interest is not fully equivalent to the expression "processing for archiving purposes in the public interest" used in the GDPR, but has a narrower scope of application.⁷

I discussed the topic with the museum curator Heidi Pelkonen. She gave me in advance the museum's collection policy⁸ that had been updated and approved and is to be published. It states that the role and the task of the museum is based on national Museum Act and one of the many aims is to store research data and make it available. It means that there is a legislative ground for archiving the sensitive interviews but at the same time it was a good reminder that the meanings of legislative terms can differ even when the context is the same.

Results

The 17 interviews of 24 interviewees have now been archived to the Regional Museum of Lapland. Among the archived interviews there is also a letter written to me by one of the interviewees, in which the interviewee describes the content of the interview in more detail (0828_00004_02).

⁷ The Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman 2026.

⁸ Kokoelmapolitiikka. To be published.

Unfortunately, it was not possible to archive one of the interviews as it was full of personal data and the anonymization would have made the interview unusable. It would probably also been possible to identify the interviewee by combining information from different sources.

When I called my interviewees some of them asked excitedly: "Are you going to make new interviews?" The memories of Petsamo are still fresh in their minds and they would like to pass on the memories for future generations. Therefore I asked cultural historian and author Virpi Vainio⁹ if she would like me to send my interviewees information about her fictional Petsamo novels and that she is doing background research for her new Petsamo novel. She wrote a short letter where she gave her contact details if someone would like to give an interview. I attached the letter to the information about the archiving as a post scriptum, clearly separated from the other information. I hope that my interviewees find this option a meaningful way to continue exploring the history of Petsamo.

I also helped one of the interviewees to archive old photographs from 1950s at the museum. Hopefully the photographs will be soon available via museum's collections.

Conclusion and evaluation

The archiving of the Petsamo interviews was a necessary step for preserving cultural heritage and for future research of the history of Petsamo and its people. The interviewees saw the research and archival of the interviews important as Petsamo people share a feeling that they had been left in the margins of history. It was important for them to raise awareness of the region and its history, and I am grateful for how encouraging and positive they have been about my research and archiving.

The research project and archiving process deepened my understanding on how to balance and navigate between regulation and legislation that keeps updating, ethical viewpoints and the principle of public interest. As a conclusion it showed how nuanced archiving sensitive research interviews can be. Ethical responsibility does not end when legislation no longer applies.

Regular contact and communication with interviewees over the years was essential as was collaboration with the Regional Museum of Lapland and its curator Heidi Pelkonen. The guidance provided by Pelkonen supported the metadata creation and made it possible to ensure that the interviews are available for future research use. This cooperation strengthened the important partnership between the University of Lapland and the museum. The process was also an important experience for my new role as Data Steward. Archiving helped me understand the intensive nature of the process and the importance of documentation.

⁹ Kirjailija Virpi Vainio 2026.

List of references

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Tietosuojalaki 1050/2018. Finlex. <https://www.finlex.fi/fi/lainsaadanto/2018/1050>

Attachment 1.

Name
0828_00001
0828_00002
0828_00003
0828_00004_01
0828_00004_02
0828_00005
0828_00006
0828_00007
0828_00008
0828_00009
0828_00010
0828_00011
0828_00012_01
0828_00012_02
0828_00013
0828_00014
0828_00015_01
0828_00015_02
0828_00015_03
0828_Asiasanat-ja-avainsanat
0828_Petsamo-tiedote_2018
0828_Petsamo-tiedote_2018_Liite-1
0828_Petsamo-tiedote_2018_Liite-2
0828_README
0828_Tiedote-arkistoinnista_2025-11-28
0828_Tiedote-arkistoinnista_2025-11-28_Liite_Vainion-tiedote
0828_Tiedote-arkistoinnista_2025-11-28_Liite-Lapin-maakuntamuseon-tietosuojaseloste

Files sent to the Regional Museum of Lapland in connection with archiving.